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Predictive factors of Uterine Rupture

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess the frequency and predictive factors of uterine rupture on no-scar uterus and on scarred uterus in an intermediate level health hospital in Dakar.

Method of study: This retrospective was carried out by the Philippe Maguilen Senghor Health Center in Yoff (Dakar) during the period from January 1, 2011 to December 31, 2017. It included all the women who gave birth there "a single pregnancy after 22 weeks of amenorrhea with a longitudinal fetal presentation or admitted after childbirth.

We had studied socio-demographic characteristics and risk factors for uterine rupture. The extracted data was analyzed first on Microsoft Excel 2016 and then on EPI info.

Results: Over 7 years, 29,332 deliveries of single pregnancies were recorded in our structure with 54 uterine ruptures, and a frequency of 0.18%. Induction of labor was spontaneous in 47 of the patients who presented with uterine rupture; labor was artificially induced in only 7 patients, with frequencies of 0.17% and 0.36% of all uterine ruptures, respectively. Considering the risk factors of uterine rupture, 5 parameters were discriminating: multiparity ($p < 0.0001$), transfer from another health facility for admission ($p < 0.0001$), type of fetal presentation ($p = 0.0001$), the presence of a uterine scar ($p < 0.0001$) and the age class ($p < 0.0001$).

Conclusion: The rate of uterine rupture in our structure is certainly low but should call for more vigilance during labor with a focus on evacuated patients who have started their work in another structure, patients with a uterine scar and multiparous. Childbirth on a scar uterus is a reasonable option after eliminating a potential cause of obstructed labor.

Keywords: Ruptured uterus; Scar uterus; Risk factors

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